

WAR AND GENOCIDE TRIGGERED BY INITIAL PRESIDENTIAL
MISREPRESENTATIONS CONSISTENT WITH THE BUTTERFLY EFFECT OF CHAOS
THEORY

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ABSTRACT

This hypothesis is based on the butterfly effect of chaos theory, which describes how a complex system's sensitivity to initial conditions can result in delayed and potentially catastrophic outcomes. **Objective:** What are the odds of "LBJ's misrepresentation contributed to My Lai massacre and Vietnam genocide?" **Method:** We applied the probability to JFK assassination and the Vietnam war to project the odds of random occurrence of "LBJ's misrepresentation in 1963 triggered the My Lai massacre in 1968?" **Results:** "LBJ's misrepresentation in 1963 triggered the My Lai massacre in 1968.

Certainty of this observation being correct is 99.99%."

- Lee Harvey Oswald was a witness at the doorway, Lee's passport was not valid for travel to Cuba, the whole Mexico City narrative was a fabrication, the extant autopsy photographs are not of the body of JFK,
- Saxitoxin, a CIA special poison arrow immobilized JFK during the ambush on 11/22/1963,
- Lucien Conien (CIA)-NSA memo reported JFK's homicide on 11/21/1963.
- Christchurch newspaper in New Zealand reported JFK's murder by Lee Harvey Oswald a lone assassin before JFK died,
- LBJ reversed JFK's NSAM 263 the military withdrawal from Vietnam on the second day of presidency.

Discussion: Mathematical evidence suggests a cause-and-effect relationship between the Coup D'etat of November 22nd, 1963 and the Vietnam War made possible by clandestine well-organized actions to sabotage JFK's presidency. The random occurrence of "a coup D'etat caused the My Lai massacre and the Vietnam War carpet bombing" is 99.99%. Evidence based history of the Vietnam war in our textbooks, museums memorials and would promote lasting peace. Conclusion: President Johnson's misrepresentations triggered the Mai Lai massacre and carpet bombing of Vietnamese civilians. Evidence based history of the Vietnam war in our textbooks, museums memorials and would promote lasting peace. War and Genocide triggered by Initial Presidential Misrepresentations Consistent with the Butterfly Effect of Chaos Theory.

INTRODUCTION

Science shall discover truth.

Hagop Saleri

Istanbul 11/22/1963

On November 22nd, 1963 President John F. Kennedy was assassinated at the Dailey Plaza in Dallas, TX.^[1,2,3,4,5] On the second day of presidency the new president Lyndon B. Johnson reversed JFK's orders to end the American military involvement in Vietnam.^[6]

The central hypothesis of this paper is "presidential lies by President Lyndon Johnson triggered the Vietnam war and My Lai massacre".

OBJECTIVE

What are the odds of "LBJ's misrepresentation of "Oswald killed JFK triggered the My Lai massacre and Vietnam genocide?"

To determine a cause and effect relationship between the coup D'etat of November 22nd, and the subsequent serial

killings of thought leaders, the My Lai Massacre and the Vietnam war and genocide.

METHOD

We reviewed data by using key words JFK assassination, Coup D'etat of November 22nd, 1963., Vietnam War through Internet search and by identifying 304 articles relevant to our investigation. We applied the probability to project the odds of random occurrence of a cause and effect of the odds of "LBJ's misrepresentation of Oswald killed JFK contributed to My Lai massacre and Vietnam genocide?"

RESULTS

Evidence of a military Coup D'etat on 11/22/1963.^[1,2,3,4]

- A. Treason.^[1,2,3,4]
- B. Constitutional crises by violation of the US Constitution.^[1,2,3,4]
- C. Ambush at the Dailey Plaza.^[1]
- D. Illegal kidnapping of JFK's body against the Texas laws to be taken to Washington D.C.^[1]
- E. JFK's autopsy photos are fake.^[3] Rivera proved that Lee was a witness in the doorway; that Lee's passport was not valid for travel to Cuba; that the whole Mexico City narrative was a fabrication; and that the extant autopsy photographs are not of the body of John Fitzgerald Kennedy.^[3,4]
- F. Bethesda Naval Hospital, surgical alterations of brain.^[2]
- G. Reversal of NSAM 263.^[3,4]
- H. Systematic silencing of witnesses and peace advocates 1963-1969 to conceal crimes against humanity.^[7-15]
- I. Destruction of crime scene evidence.^[1]
- J. Profound differences between the official narratives vs, historical evidence.^[1]

A. Treason

1. Treason #1

Mc George Bundy reversed JFK's Bay of Pigs orders for air support for Cuban rebels. General Taylor's committee concluded that Bundy's reversal of JFK's orders was the most critical error for the Bay of Pigs disaster.^[6]

2. Treason #2

August 1963 cable from Hilsman green light for a Vietnamese Coup D'etat undermining JFK's Vietnam exit strategy.^[16]

3. Treason #3

On 10/1963, Bundy aid Forrestal delivered a memo to Ambassador Lodge authorizing Coup D'etat in Vietnam undermining JFK's Vietnam strategy.^[16]

4. Treason #4

11/01/1963 Conein in Saigon, Bundy from the White House Situation Room participated in a Coup D'etat in Vietnam.^[6,17]

5. Treason #5

On 11/01/1963, Diem brothers were murdered Despite specific JFK's orders for safe exit.^[6,17]

6. Treason #6

Saxitoxin a specialty weapon developed by the CIA assisted JFK's getting immobilized and becoming a stationary target for ambush on 11/22/1963.^[18,19,20]

7. Treason #7

Colby was silenced after his 1975 testimony before the Senate intelligence committee consistent with "saxitoxin immobilized JFK at the Dealey Plaza"^[18,19,20]

8. Treason #8

NSA memo 11/21/1963 authored by Lucien Conein, top secret of JFK's death a day before 11/22/1963.^[21]

9. Treason #10

JFK's brain was operated at the Bethesda Naval Hospital proven by David Mantik Ph.D., M.D.^[2]

B. Constitutional Crises by Violation of the US Constitution.

Treason (Table A,B,C,D,E)

Coup D'etat (A,B,C,D,E).

Serial killings by CIA assets^[7-15]

C. Perfect concealment of crimes against humanity by destruction of crime scene evidence^[1,2] (image A).

D. Profound differences between the official narratives vs, historical evidence.^[1]

Ode to joy, Salerian AJ Oil painting celebrating WHD 09/21/2025

Table A

Executive Actions Consistent with Execua Coup D'etat

- A. Secret Service washing the presidential limousine to get rid of criminal evidence.
- B. Secret Service. No protection.
- C. Secret Service lost JFK's brain and human tissues.

- D. Surgery at Bethesda. Naval Hospital to alter JFK's brain.
- E. LBJ misrepresentations of Oswald and a nuclear confrontation with the Soviet Union.
- F. A CIA developed poison arrow saxitoxin to paralyze the president during the ambush.
- G. Conein/NSA MEMO 11/21/1963 Jfk is dead

Table B

Coup D'etat and Treason= Odds of certainty 99.999%
 "Coup D'etat caused the Vietnam War "consistent with
 17 Independent violations of the US Constitution.

Treason #1

Mac Bundy reversed JFK's Bay of Pig orders for air support for Cuban rebels. General Taylor's committee concluded that Bundy's reversal of JFK's orders was the most critical error for the Bay of Pigs disaster.

Treason #2

Bundy aid Hillsman sent an August 1963 Cable authorizing a Vietnamese Coup D'etat against JFK's strategy.

Treason #3

Bundy aid Forrestal delivered a memo to Ambassador Lodge authorizing Coup D'etat Vietnam against JFK's strategy, 10/1963.

Treason #4

Conein in Saigon, Bundy from the White House Situation Room executed a coup d'etat in Vietnam. 11/01/1963.

Treason #5

Despite specific orders for safe exit by President Kennedy Diem brothers were murdered. 11/01/1963.

Treason #6

Saxitoxin a specialty weapon developed by the CIA assisted JFK's getting immobilized and becoming a stationary target for ambush. 11/22/1963

Treason #7

Colby was Silenced after his Senate testimony confirming that saxitoxin immobilized JFK at the Dealey Plaza.

Treason #8

NSA memo 11/21/1963 authored by Lucien Conein, top secret of JFK's death one day before he was killed.

Treason #9

Photographic alterations to James Atkins AP images to frame Oswald as the patsy proven fraudulent by the extraordinary photographic research by Larry Rivera.

Treason #10

JFK's brain was operated at the Bethesda Naval Hospital.

Treason #11.

No Secret Service protection. A key Secret Service agent left behind at the airport.

Treason #12

Crime scene evidence altered. Crime scene washed. Brain and tissue samples lost.

Treason #13

Vanishing JFK Tapes. Of JFK, November, White House. Under the custody of Bundy.

Treason #14

Deliberate deception. JFK 's Cabinet away.

Treason 15

New Zealand Paper Christchurch publishing Oswald killed JFK before JFK died.

Treason 16

Physically impossible.: Magic bullet of Kennedy and Connolly traveling and jumping through bodies without any damage to the bullet.

Treason 17

Unethical Conflict of interest inclusion of Allen Dulles in the Warren Committee.

Table C

No Written Presidential Authorization for Coup D'etat/ GSSH / Vietnam

- A. No written presidential authorization for GSSH of JFK, RFK, MLK. John Lennon, Stanley Kubrick. Gus Grissom, Thomas Baron, Ed White, Roger Chafee.
- B. No written Presidential authorization to Keep the Pacific commanders and 3500 men unaware of the no surprise. Japanese Pearl Harbor assault because of broken military codes
- C. No written Presidential orders to cover up of the Katyn Massacre of 20000 Polish POW's by Stalin.
- D. No written Presidential orders to authorize the atomic bombing of Hiroshima residents.
- E. No written Presidential orders to authorize the atomic bombing of Hiroshima residents.
- F. No written Presidential orders authorizing the bombing of Dresden residents.
- G. No written Presidential orders authorizing the bombing of Tokyo residents.
- H. No written Presidential orders authorizing civilian bombings.

Table D

GSSH Signature traits

1. Sudden premature death.
2. Killer or killers never face justice to spite.
3. Scientific evidence
4. Medical evidence incompatible with official narrative.
5. Lost or falsified records

6. Sudden suspicious deaths of people. With crucial information.
7. Cover up.
8. Numerous mechanical mishaps or human errors.

Plausible deniability, Justice system based upon reasonable doubt void of scientific certainty.

Dead whistleblowers.

Dead witnesses,

Dead officials who testify before Congress.

Dad. Newspaper reporters. Said confessors of crimes friends family assoc

iates aware of dead heroes assets would nonexistent ties to a government agency st

Table E

Why is it difficult to diagnose GSSH?

No return records.

False records, destroyed records,

IMAGE A

Secret Service washing off crime scene evidence. Before Jeff Gays declared dead

Table F

Mc George Bundy Errors

1. Refused to write a mandatory essay for college entry; was admitted to Yale.
2. Former assistant to Allen Dulles
3. Cheated eye exam to enter the army.
4. Member codebreaking/decoding team London.
5. The only professor of history at Harvard without a PhD.
6. FBI' Chief asset to cleanse Harvard of Reds.

7. The only professor of history at Harvard without a PhD.

8. National Security adviser to the president.

9. General Maxwell Taylor; Chair /Committee on Bay of Pigs o concluded that Bundy/s decision to reverse JFK's orders for air cover for the Cuban freedom fighters, was the single most important cause of the fiasco.

10. A few shattered glasses, no big deal, Bundy joked the day after "Bay of Pigs".

11. A cable from Hillsman 908/1963) and a handwritten note delivered by Forrestal (11/1963) both unauthorized by JFK Ambassador Lodge get a green light for a Coup D'etat in Vietnam.
12. From the White House situation on November 1st, 1963 Mac George Bundy and Conien in Saigon jointly monitored Diem Brothers in violation of JFK's orders for safe exit.

Table G

Would America Go to War if We Knew--?
 Pearl Harbor was no surprise
 Stalin's had no army.
 Atrocities by Stalin
 Katyn Massacre by Stalin
 European Wars: Civilian bombings SOP

Table H

What if FDR did not enter the war?
 America may still be the leader of the world because of her Scientific and military Supremacy.

Table I

FDR's Misrepresentations and Outcome	
FDR	Outcome
Silent Military aid	Soviet Union/Superpower
Pearl Harbor lie	72 m dead
Manhattan Project	Hiroshima/Nagasaki 200.000
Civilian bombings and coverup	Dresden/Hamburg/Tokyo 250.000
Katyn massacre coverup	20.000 polish POW skulls crushed
Pearl Harbor /Hitler crimes	Israel

LBJ's Misrepresentations and Outcome

Oswald killed JFK	My Lai Massacre
Nuclear war if LHO not guilty	Vietnam war and genocide

Salerian AJ, Good News from Heaven.: Evidence Based War and Space Museums and Modern Gladiators at the White House, California Courier06/16/26.

DISCUSSION

Dailey Plaza was a man made disaster meticulously planned and executed with military excellence. Astonishingly, the world wrongly believed JFK was killed by a lone assassin, a former CIA agent, an obvious patsy, with his top secret background published in Christ Church newspaper in New Zealand before JFK died.

The Coup D'etat of 1963 followed the tragic Second world war. FDR modernized the Soviet army upgrading the Soviet Union to become a military superpower.^[22] FDR never informed the Pacific commanders of his foreknowledge of the Japanese assault on Pearl Harbor.^[22,23] He covered up the Katyn massacre by Stalin.^[22] FDR and Churchill covered up Stalin's atrocities.^[22] Truman knew very little about the Manhattan Project did not- in writing authorize Hiroshima and Nagasaki.^[24] The bloody Second World

War secrets remained undercover after the assassination of James Forrestal, the First Secretary of Defense.^[25,26] (Table (G,H,I).

It is my lucky discovery to observe that the butterfly effect of sensitive dependence of complex systems on Initial conditions can trigger delayed catastrophic events mediate human behavior and wars and genocide.

Should we surprised that the physical and thermodynamic laws of universe govern human biology wars and peace on earth ?^[27,28]

We are complex chemical entities governed by physical laws; our philosophical scientific religious moral beliefs and behavior are shaped by environmental influences: Talat pasha lies triggered the Armenian genocide in 1915.^[29,30,31,32,33] FDR lies of Pearl Harbor triggered genocide of Hiroshima and Nagasaki residents. LBJ lies about Lee Harvey Oswald triggered the My Lai massacre in 1968.

Bundy and Conien were the operational chiefs of the assassinations of Diem Brothers, John F Kennedy and Robert F Kennedy and possibly others. Bundy from the situation Room at the White House, Conien in Saigon on 11/01/1963 and on Main street, Dallas, TX on 11/22/1963 were the masterminds of both assassinations.

JFK's foreign policy;" Diplomacy first, war only when the US national security is in danger." was consistently sabotaged by JFK insiders Mc George Bundy, Michael Forrestal, Roger Hilsman, tactfully documented by Robert McNamara, In retrospect.^[13]

It seems that scientifically inaccurate narratives of the Vietnam War by our text books, national museums, monuments limit our ability to learn from past presidential mistakes have been counterproductive for lasting peace by suppressing scientific evidence.

In addition to hundreds of serial killings by government sanctioned homicides the My Lai massacre and the carpet bombing of Vietnamese were concealed under presidential lies that the war in Vietnam was necessary to stop communism.

Collectively fake news - Wikipedia and government propaganda- disseminate inaccurate information about past tragedies.

Inaccurate information about past tragedies caused by LBJ's ambush of JFK at the Dailey Plaza that silenced hundreds of peace advocates by GHHS before carpet bombing Vietnamese and massacring 302 and women and children in My Lai.

Even the most eloquent healing message cannot fully diminish the endured by a large number of researchers dedicated to the Hippocratic spirit, science and the

American Constitution. They all say Integrity matters, for lasting peace our museums memorials and textbooks must be rooted in evidence based history of the Vietnam war.

Less than perfect integrity is pregnant for disaster. For lasting peace our museums memorials and textbooks must be rooted in evidence based history of the Vietnam war.

Consistent with the probability theory," the odds of a coup D'etat caused the My Lai massacre and the Vietnam War carpet bombing "is not a random occurrence %99.99.

Textbooks, museums, and memorials would foster enduring peace by disseminating evidence based history.^[83]

CONCLUSION

President Johnson's misrepresentations triggered the Mai Lai massacre and carpet bombing of Vietnamese civilians.

Textbooks, museums, and memorials would foster enduring peace by disseminating evidence based history.

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